

Are Newton's Laws Lawful?

Abstract

The paper challenges Newton's 2nd and 3rd laws through an ether-vortex model. Matter is viewed as a system of two interconnected ether toroids. **Inertness** is defined as a delayed reaction of this system to deformation, proving that forces and reactions are never equal in dynamic processes. The author suggests replacing algebraic laws with differential equations to reveal the physical nature of motion. This work establishes the foundational model of the ether as a continuous medium and describes elementary particles as stable toroidal vortices.

A viewpoint is presented on physical laws as a temporary measure of misunderstanding and the inability to explain their essence. Based on the principle of short-range interaction and the concept of an ether medium in the form of massless discrete elements, an attempt is made to show the erroneous nature of Newton's second and third laws.

We will focus on two of Newton's laws — the second and the third. Although, by and large, it makes sense to discuss not just the "lawfulness" of physical laws, but the triumph of positivist ideology in physics and the complete victory of the phenomenological approach. Physics is presented solely as a form of mathematical description, often based on questionable postulates, without an understanding of the physical essence of phenomena. And at the origins of this stood the great I. Newton himself.

To clarify the truth or fallacy of these two laws, let us turn to the physical essence of the phenomenon of **inertness**. We are guided by the idea of short-range interaction based on an ether medium, a concept developed by thinkers such as Descartes and Kant, and physicists such as Faraday, Maxwell, Kelvin, and Mitkevich.

Let us begin with a hypothetical model of elementary particles of matter, which represent a time-stable, closed vortex motion of the ether in the form of a toroid. Such motion induces a vortex motion of the surrounding ether, also in the form of a larger toroid, but with a cavity for the internal vortex. These two motions are interconnected and, in the absence of external influences, are in a state of stable equilibrium according to the Le Chatelier-Braun principle.

This means that upon relative displacement due to changes in shape, volume, and relative position, a counteraction arises. Since the "embryo" of the particle is PURELY internal motion, it can only be affected by acting on the external motion. Therefore, any **deformation** of the external motion or deviation from equilibrium (their relative displacement) causes a forceful counteraction. These two motions are a single whole. This phenomenon is the essence of both inertial and gravitational mass; they are physically indistinguishable.

From the standpoint of this model, the essence of inertness is clear: during the **deformation** of the outer toroid, a relative displacement of the outer relative to the inner occurs, and a forceful counteraction arises from the equilibrium state, manifesting as resistance. A real force of inertness arises, counteracting the change in equilibrium. Thus, inertial mass is the interconnection of two closed vortex motions that forcefully counteract the violation of their equilibrium.

The process of interaction with a particle is described as follows: if the deformation is imagined as a step with a negligibly short rise time, then the reaction force — the force of

inertness — arises with some delay due to the finite time of interaction between the two motions. The process of its change over time will have an oscillatory character, typical for feedback processes with a delay.

As follows from these arguments, the deformation and the force of inertness (the reaction force) are not equal in time. From this, it follows that Newton's third law is not legitimate to apply in dynamic processes. For dynamic processes, it is erroneous.

Since deformations applied to the external motion should be regarded as applied to the particle itself, the force of inertness is not accounted for in the mathematical notation of Newton's second law. Newton's second law is fundamentally erroneous. Its equation should not be algebraic, but differential. This will reflect the oscillatory nature of the interaction. Without this, it is impossible to understand the physical reason for Newton's first law (uniform rectilinear motion).

The elastic properties of matter and the emergence of elastic waves are also caused by this nature of delayed reaction within the material.

References

1. Kuzmin I. N., "Are Newton's Laws Legitimate?" (Electronic resource), 2011, URL: kulichki.net